

PerceptEarth: Global Layers of Human Urban Perception Derived from AlphaEarth Foundations Satellite Embeddings

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Abstract. In this study, we propose a scalable pipeline that links human perception data from the Place Pulse project with AlphaEarth satellite embedding representations to explore whether human perceptions of urban environments, such as beauty, safety, and liveliness, can be transferred to global coverage. The overarching aim is to investigate whether large-scale, remotely sensed contextual and environmental features encoded in satellite embeddings can approximate patterns in human visual perception that are traditionally measured using ground-level imagery and human evaluations.

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BoK Concepts. [GC3], [GC2], [IP3]

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1 Methods

We start from the Place Pulse dataset, which contains human pairwise comparisons of street-level scenes along perception dimensions such as beauty and safety, collected from more than 50 cities and comprising over 1 million preferences (Dubey et al., 2016). Rather than treating these comparisons as direct ratings, we aggregate them into continuous image-level latent perception scores using a ranking-based approach. TrueSkill is used to infer a relative latent score for each geolocated image based on its comparison outcomes within the broader judgment graph (Herbrich et al., 2006). These latent scores are then normalized to a 0 to 10 index to facilitate downstream modelling and interpretation, while remaining explicitly relative rather than absolute measures of perception.

To connect street-level perceptual signals with remotely sensed data, we extract satellite embedding features at the locations of Place Pulse images using AlphaEarth Foundations representations (Brown et al., 2025). These embeddings summarize multispectral and spatial patterns in the built and natural environment but are defined at the pixel level. To better reflect the fact that human perception is shaped by surrounding context rather than a single point, we extend the embeddings spatially by computing multi-scale neighbourhood descriptors. For multiple radii around each image location, we calculate distance-decayed weighted statistics, including the mean and standard deviation of each embedding dimension. A negative exponential decay function is used so that nearby context contributes more strongly than distant areas. This results in a hierarchical representation that captures both immediate local conditions and broader neighbourhood character.

Using these engineered features, we outline a supervised learning framework in which gradient boosting regression models are trained to predict the normalized perception index from satellite embedding descriptors. Model evaluation is designed to emphasize generalization rather than memorization, using spatially informed data splits that limit information leakage, such as withholding entire cities or large spatial regions during validation. This setup allows us to assess whether learned relationships transfer to unseen urban contexts rather than reflecting local visual similarities alone.

2 Outcome

Applying the trained model to satellite embeddings globally, we produce continuous raster surfaces of predicted perception indices. These global layers, intended to be released for open use, provide a new class

of perception-informed covariates that can be directly integrated into large-scale urban analytics, comparative regional studies, and equity-oriented research. This enables empirical investigation of perceptual dimensions at spatial extents and resolutions that have not previously been accessible.

3 Data and Software Availability

The resulting global raster surfaces will be made publicly available after completion of model validation and quality control procedures.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were utilized for language editing but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

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